

NEOLOGISMS AND WAYS OF THEIR FORMATION IN THE ENGLISH
LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the description of the features of the formation of new words in the English language. The article discusses such ways of forming new words in the English language as suffixation and prefix, word composition, conversion, abbreviation, loan, abbreviation and other ways of forming neologisms. In addition, the author in the article also dwells on the peculiarities of the translation of neologisms.

KEYWORDS: language; word formation; suffixation; prefixation; word composition; neologisms; English language; borrowing of words; abbreviation.

Linguist1 is very sensitive to all the trends that take place in society (see, for example, [Popova 2003: 37-41]). Thus, T. G. Popova and E. V. Kurochkina note that for language it is important to "have a sensitive sense of objects and phenomena of real reality based on personal subjective perception of the surrounding world and linguistic and social experience" [Popova, Kurochkina 2014: 68-75]. Starting to highlight the issues that are related to the issues of neologisms, we note that their morphological structure and the nature of the meaning are formed in line with the word-formation traditions of a particular language. Thus, new words appear in the language when the need for neologism is realized. The modern English language has many ways of forming new words, which include word addition, conversion, abbreviations, adjectivization, substantiation, reverse word formation, lexico-semantic method, alternation of sounds and stress transfer in a word (phonological method), etc. However, at the same time it should be noted that not all of these methods are used to the same extent, and the specific weight of each of them in the word-formation process is not the same. We will focus on the following most common of these ways of forming neologisms:

- affixal method (prefixal and suffixal methods);
- word composition;
- conversion;
- reduction;
- borrowing from other languages;
- reverse derivation;
- fusion;

□ abbreviation.

Next, we will talk about each of them in more detail. Affixal units, according to Cannon, make up 24% of all neoplasms and are slightly inferior to complex words [Cannon 1986: 732]. Here it is also necessary to identify prefix units, which clearly demonstrate the increased role of prefixes. The main source of prefixes is Latin, French and Greek: the prefix mega-, which acts as a strong particle, is extremely popular in American informal communication. In recent years, this prefix has been actively used in the vocabulary of teenagers. For example, to express the highest assessment of an event, phenomenon, or person, the word megadual (totally awesome) is used - "something extremely good". Dual in this case is used in the meaning "twice as good" [Zabotkina 1989: 38].

Suffixal units are more commonly used in everyday communication and are more marked by the word "slang". So, one of the most common slang suffixes is the suffix -y/-ie, (ironic meaning). The words formed with its help are limited in use by the framework of informal communication, mainly among young people. For example, let's give an English word like groupie, which translates into English as "a fan of a pop ensemble or a star accompanying them everywhere." In addition to the lexical unit groupie already mentioned, it is possible to point out as an example such a widely used word in the field of musicians as roadie, which in Russian translates as "a member of a group of musicians responsible for the transportation and installation of equipment." Let's also give as an example a word like weepy, which translates into Russian as "sentimental film". You can also cite an English word like preppie, which translates into Russian as "a student of a private private school." Note that this word is used ironically by representatives of the middle class.

Conversion as a way of creating new words has now significantly decreased its activity and is inferior to all other types of word formation. Conversion is the transition of a word from one part of speech to another. So, for example, now on the Internet you can often see the E-mail me/us to. It is not difficult to understand the meaning of such a neologism. The syntactic context makes it possible to determine whether the word belongs to transitional chapters, and, accordingly, knowing the meaning of the word E-mail (electronic mail), we translate the English sentence "E-mail me/us to" into Russian as "Send me (us) messages by electronic mail address".

Among converted nouns, there is an increasing tendency to form verbs with postpositions: rip-off – "theft" (from to rip-off – "steal"). A significant number of new nouns are formed by conversion from adjectives, for example: collectables - "objects to be collectible, especially outdated or rare"; cool – "self-control, restraint" is often used in phrases such as "to lose one's cool", "to keep one's cool", which in Russian translates as, "lose control, hold back."

The formation of nouns from adjectives ending in -ic is especially productive, for example: acrylic, transuranic, tricyclic. Nouns can be formed from verbal phrases, for example: work-to-rule – "the performance of workers with the requirements to comply with all clauses of the employment contract" [Breus 2001: 123]. When nouns are formed from adjectives at the semantic level, the seme "quality" is muted and the seme "object" is added, which becomes the center of the meaning of the substantive unit: acrylic – "acrylic (synthetic material)". Thus, we can conclude that the conversion enriches the content of the concept.

The next conclusion that we come to is that, according to the territorial parameter, the new converted units are limited mainly by the American version and, therefore, to a lesser extent by the British version of the English language.

The next way to actively form new words in modern English is to shorten them. In this regard, it seems important to note that among the irregular ways of forming morphological neologisms, the most productive in the last decade have been abbreviations that reflect the tendency to rationalize language, to save linguistic efforts. However, despite the fact that abbreviations make up only a small percentage of the total number of neologisms, their number is still growing quite actively. For example, of the four types of abbreviations, and they include abbreviations, acronyms, truncations, and merges, truncated words predominate. In this regard, we will cite such a word as anchor < anchorman, which in Russian translates as "a news columnist coordinating TV or radio programs." It is important to note here that this word is limited in use by the American version, whereas in the British version it corresponds to the word presenter, lib < liberation.

Next, we will focus on such a way of forming new words in the English language as borrowing from other languages. In this regard, first of all, it should be emphasized that borrowing from other languages and linguistic cultures at the present stage of language development is one of the most common ways of forming new words. Here is an example of using borrowed words in the absence of an identical word in the translation language: "The Soviets had Sputnik, but the Americans had their open-plan kitchen. No contest", which translates into Russian as "The Soviet Union created Sputnik, and the Americans created an open kitchen. Out of competition" [cit. by: Barkhudarov 2005: 47]. The next way to form new words in the English language is such a method as reverse derivation, which is the process of forming verbs by truncating the suffix from correlative nouns. As an example, we will give such a widely represented English word as televise, which is translated into Russian as "show on television". The English word televise, which is formed by reverse derivation from the full version of the

word, originates from the full version of the lexical unit "television", which translates as "television".

Thus, having considered the features of neologisms and the most common ways of forming new words in the English language, we come to the conclusion that neologisms in the English language are formed according to the laws of the English language, according to its productive models of word formation. However, at the same time, we must also note the rather important fact that new words that appear in the literary and book sublanguage are sometimes created by the most diverse and unproductive ways of word formation. But this circumstance has its positive sides. This can be explained by the fact that in cases of active use of the language of a wide variety of ways of word formation, the very effective power of word-forming means becomes much more pronounced, much clearer and, of course, more tangible. It is in connection with this circumstance that the very means of forming new words often act as a stylistic device. We also find confirmation of our thoughts in the work of I. V. Arnold [Arnold 2003: 59].

On the other hand, the formation of the semantics of neologism is the result of linguistic and creative activity associated with the transition of a new unit from individual specific use to use by the linguistic community. Thus, accordingly, the most characteristic ways of forming neologisms in modern English are word composition, conversion and changing the meanings of words.

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